

Mitigation of Stellar Activity in Radial Velocity Data Using Gaussian Process Regression : I. Understanding of the Relationship Between Photometric Variation and Stellar Activity

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Abstract: With the development of next generation spectrograph underway, the main limitations of the radial velocity method is not only restricted to the accuracy of the instrument, but also the effects of mimic-planetary signals created by stellar activity. Although current Gaussian Process (GP) methods have many advantages to solving this issue and have successfully remedied the issue in some cases, the physical meaning of hyperparameters of GP, the false positive rate of this method and its efficiency are still mysterious to us. In this master project, we develop a fast simulation model in Julia programming language which includes the effects of stellar spots and plages. We then use this model to test the efficiency and applicable range of GP method.

1. Introduction

The radial velocity technique is the indirect method used to detect planets orbiting a central star by observing the periodic wobble movement of the star. A lot of successful results have been obtained with this method. It is strongly believed that with the development of next generation spectrograph and the complementary data from space photometry telescopes, e.g. the on-going TESS [43] and upcoming PLATO [42], the RV method has great potential for discovering a remarkable diversity of planetary systems.

However, if current RV techniques want to push the detection limit to small planets in solar-like stars, $m \cdot s^{-1}$ level has been achieved with the most precise spectrograph, there will need to be a way to model stellar activity. More explicitly, the number of discoverable planets in a given system heavily depends on the fitting model people chosen. In order to maximize the number of planets to be detected in RV and guarantee the accuracy of their orbital parameters simultaneously, we need a way to model stellar activity properly[9].

Although stellar oscillation can be smoothed by setting an exposure time to 10-15 minutes, it is still challenging to remove the perturbation from granulation, especially supergranulation, which has a strong effect on Earth-twin detectability [30, 12, 29]. For short-term activity like spots and plages, they can make cm/s to several m/s contributions to the observed RV variations [28, 31].

In such a situation, Gaussian Process(GP) was proposed as one of the correction techniques to deal with mitigation stellar activity in RV. GP, as a non-parametric way to mitigate the contribution of stellar activity, has been applied to many cases of RV data reduction [19, 17, 36, 5, 6, 8, 40, 7, 45, 20, 41, 14]

Currently, there are two GP frameworks for the RV fitting problem. The first is based on Haywood et al. [19]. It applies a GP regression to short-term activity first, e.g. photometry flux or activity index ($\log(R'_{HK})$) and then assumes that RV variations have the same covariance properties with activity time series. A second GP regression is applied which has the same covariance structure as the RV data. This GP absorbs correlated noise due to the stellar activity through a global fit (Keplerian signals + GP).

The second method is inspired from the approximate analytic relationship between photometry and RV from spots and plage, which denotes as FF' method[2]. And it was officially proposed as a routine to real fitting problem in Rajpaul et al. [41]. Rather using single proxy, this GP framework models all time series ($\log(R'_{HK})$, FWHM, BIS SPAN, RV) simultaneously using the combination of a hidden GP and its derivative to fit all data. This combination comes from the FF' method.

However, there exists some issues and unknown process of these two GP framework. One of the drawbacks is that RV variations may not have the same covariance behavior of activity proxy. An intuition is that a $P_{rot}/2$ sinusoidal signal from the RV caused by spots definitely has a difference in covariance information compared with the corresponding variation with period as P_{rot} in activity proxy [10]. Even for the second one, which is more statistically robust, there are still a lot of steps to make it convincable enough to apply to real world. For

example, a more realistic relationship should be developed based on theoretical or empirical considerations. A physical motivated GP covariance function will be the key point to approach the real fitting situation. Also, limited understanding of hyperparameters in GP function can be a barrier for the understanding of fitting performances [41].

2. Motivations

In order to make GP more robust towards this fitting problem and test its efficiency, we basically setup a hare-and-hound exercise, where we develop a simulation for stellar activity using lightcurves and RVs. The simulation should be as close to a real situation as much as possible. We display our simulation results and GP rotation measurement in 2.1. Then we focus on a more physical motivated GP covariance function, called stochastic harmonic oscillation (SHO) function (first proposed in Foreman-Mackey et al. [15]), to test its performances towards different situations. We illustrate the physical motivation of using such Gaussian kernel attacking this problem through an analysis from solar total irradiance observation in 2.2. Finally, we apply the first GP framework mentioned in introduction, which takes GP component as the complete contribution of stellar activity, towards the TOU RV fitting of a benchmark star HD115403 with known planet orbital and stellar activity in 2.3.

2.1. The Hare: Tool for Photometry and RV Variability Induced by Stellar Activity

Compared with a stellar activity simulation code SOAP2.0, developed by Geneva group [11], our simulation code in Julia programming language directly map the spots and plage from surface to the time series instead of deriving photometry and RV variance from the cross correlation function (CCF) of stellar spectrum.

We basically follow Aigrain et al. [2] routine to get the flux variation from spots rotation and evolution but does not that their calculation of butterfly diagram which is more realer. We hope to implement in our future version of code. If we take the latitude of each spots θ_k according to a linear butterfly diagram with the initial phase t_0 and cycle length L_{cyc} . The distribution of the latitudes match with a bimodal distribution with their average equals with $\theta_k(t, t_0, L_{cyc})$ (northern semisphere) and $-\theta_k(t, t_0, L_{cyc})$ (southern semisphere) individually. The weight of these two components are both 0.5, which means that they have the same chance to appear at both semispheres. We set a dispersion about 2.5 degree for each components in the bimodal normal distribution to allow some scattering and randomness of it. Here k means the k th spots in our simulation.

Then we consider the differential which is assemble with the Sun-like differential ones by setting the rotation rate as:

$$\Omega(\theta_k) = \Omega_{eq} [1 - \delta \sin^2(\theta_k)] \quad (1)$$

where $\Omega_{eq} = 2\pi/P_{eq}$, is the rotation frequency at the equator. δ is the differential rotation rate injected by user, usually tends to adopt positive values smaller than 0.5. Therefore the rotation period for each spots we generated is $P_k = 2\pi/\Omega(\theta_k)$

We followed the analytical formulae in Aigrain et al. [2] to calculate the temporal variability of single spots:

$$\Delta F(t) = -A_{max} f_k(t) MAX\{\mu_k(t), 0\} [c_s + qc_f (1 - \mu_k(t))] \quad (2)$$

where A_{max} is the proportionality choosen by user to match with the amplitude of their observational light curves. c_s and c_f are the contrast of spots and faculae individually. q is the fractional area of faculae $\mu_k(t)$ is the angle between the line of sight and spot normal, which can be write more specifically:

$$\cos \mu_k(t) = \cos \phi_k \cos \theta_k \cos i + \sin \theta_k \sin i \quad (3)$$

where i is the star spin axis inclination angle (the angle between the stars rotation axis and the line of sight), θ_k is the spot latitude relative to the stellar equator and ϕ_k is relative phase longitude of spots to the line of sight, which can be written as $\phi_k(t) = 2\pi(t - t_k)/P_k + \phi_k^{(0)}$.

Here $f_k(t)$ take the effect of spots evolution into account for the variation of spots areas, we simply take the linear mode for the coming and dying of the spots as:

$$f_k(t) = \begin{cases} \frac{3}{\tau_s}(t - t_k) + 1, & t_k - \frac{1}{3}\tau_s < t < t_k; \\ -\frac{3}{2\tau_s}(t - t_k) + 1, & t_k < t < t_k + \frac{2}{3}\tau_s \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

τ_s is the lifetime of spots sampled from a multi-modal normal distribution, which is described in the following part.

The largest advantage of this is that we require less computational resources to create large amounts of spots but a trade-off would be lack of simulation of other spectral variations such as FWHM, BIS and SPAN. In our future version of this code, we intend to implement these functions from analytical or empirical consideration. This is an open-source code, which can be found at [Jspot](#). A few features about our code:

- **Simulate large amounts of spots and plages**
- **Consider suppression of convection blueshift by spots and plages**
- **Implement the evolution of spots and plages, including lifetime and butterfly diagram**
- **Fast speed compared with SOAP2.0 with creating the same number of spots and plages**

One of the strength of [Jspot](#) is that we can simulate star spots emergence and decay behavior. After checking with previous literature about the relationship between spotslifetime and rotation periods [37, 38], for non-solar spots, we set the distribution of lifetime as: $\tau_{spots} = P_{rot} 2.73^{|\alpha|}$ where $\alpha \sim \mathcal{N}(ofs, ds)$, and ofs is the offset value for the mean of spotslifetimes and ds is the standard deviation from its mean value; Since we have direct records for sun spots lifetime we can create its distribution using observations from Howard [21], Dumusque [9]:

- 50% of the spot groups have lifetimes of between 1 h and 2 days;
- 40% of the spot groups have lifetimes of between 2 days and 11 days; and
- 10% of the spot groups have lifetimes of between 11 days and 2 months.

In order to simulate more situations, we also apply a scale factor to the boundary in for each group.

We set the contrast of spots to the background flux as 0.2 and the contrast for plages as 2. Therefore the ratio between the plages and spots is around 4. We also set the convection depression from the spots/plages to 2km/s per area. The input periods of our simulation are all 25.05 days, which is the mean of solar surface rotation period. We display our fitting results towards non-solar spots scenarios in Fig1 with different combinations of offset and decay scale. We notice that the photometry and RV time series gradually lost periodicity with decreasing the offset, which is the direction of decreasing the star spots lifetime. Increasing the decay scale can include more spots having large lifetime and make the time series appearing with solar-like periodicity. Interesting, by comparing the periodicity behavior between variation of flux and RV with one certain distribution setup, we also discover that the flux effect from spots is nearly compensated by the effect of plages, which can be explained by spots being fainter and plages being brighter than the solar quiet photosphere. While for RV, both spots and plages contributes to the convection blue-shift.

2.2. Fitting stellar spots activity in photometry simulation lightcurves

We use the Julia code we mentioned in 2.1 to simulate a large quantity of photometry and corresponding radial velocity time series data to test our GP performances for different scenarios. Currently, our code currently can only recover variations from spots and plages. This means that we are unable to consider the effect of convective granulations. Here we take solar simulation as sample in Fig.2(a) We modify the input period in the lightcurves and take blind fitting towards them. We find that by using our GP fitting program, we can perfectly recover stellar activity caused by sun spots in slow rotators (rotation periods are larger than 3 days). Fig2(b) and Fig2(c) displays our fitting performances.

2.3. The Hound: Accurate GP Routine for RV Mitigation

The physical meaning of the current GP kernel used by the community still lacks detailed explanation. An explanation of the physical intuition-motivated GP kernel need to be explored first. Historically, Harvey [18], Michel et al. [34], Mathur et al. [27], Kallinger et al. [24] found that the following empirical profile or the combination of it can fit the power spectral density (PSD) of super-granulation and granulation variation:

$$P_i(\nu) = \frac{A_i}{1 + (B_i \nu_i)^{C_i}} \quad (5)$$

Foreman-Mackey et al. [15] found that the summation of two Stochastic Harmonica Oscillator(SHO) term kernels can perfectly model the stellar activity:

$$S(\omega) = \sqrt{\frac{2}{\pi}} \frac{S_0 \omega_0^4}{(\omega^2 - \omega_0^2)^2 + \omega_0^2 \omega^2 / Q^2} \quad (6)$$

Figure 1: These two plots show that different impact of spots lifetime distribution to the periodicity of flux and RV variation time series. We explore visually the effects from the offset, dispersion of the distribution relative to the rotation period, and the effects of the contrast of faculae (here c_f just indicates the proportionality relative to solar observations 0.115, e.g. $c_f = 3$ means the injected $c_f = 0.345$). All simulation are injected with the solar rotation period: 25.05 days. There are major conclusion we can derive from them: the existence of plages affect the real periodicity derived by surface rotation and increasing the decay scale can include more spots having large lifetime and make the time series appearing with the true rotation period. Increasing the contrast of faculae makes the real rotation period blurred in the light curve and makes it tend to rotate in its nth harmonic period, e.g the topest with $c_f = 3$ even if its spots lifetime is much longer than the true rotation period.

Figure 2: (a) We use [Jspot](#) to simulate total solar irradiance and corresponding radial velocity considering the effect of sun spots, plages, butterfly diagram and differential rotation; (b) We inject rotation period into the simulated lightcurves and measure their rotation period using Gaussian Process, from which we can perfectly recover periods from 3 to 80 days. It is noticeable that we do not consider the effect of lifetime here, so every spots in these simulations never die down in the whole simulation time span; (c) is a look at the fitting performance, which has very small residual after subtracting our fitting model

S_0, Q, ω_0 are hyperparameters. For rotation term,

$$\begin{cases} Q_1 = 0.5 + Q_0 + \Delta Q, \omega_1 = \frac{4\pi Q_1}{P\sqrt{4Q_1^2 - 1}}, S_1 = \frac{H}{\omega_1 Q_1} \\ Q_2 = 0.5 + Q_0, \omega_2 = \frac{8\pi Q_2}{P\sqrt{4Q_2^2 - 1}}, S_2 = m \frac{H}{\omega_2 Q_2} \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

P is period, Q_0 and ΔQ are hyper-parameters about modes of oscillation frequency, H is the amplitude of the variability and m is the fractional amplitude of the secondary mode compared to the primary and should probably always be $0 < m < 1$.

The reason behind this is not surprising: according to some previous observations of sun and other stars light curves with apparent existence of spots, people find that some star spots emergence at longitudes with a difference of 180 degrees, which might have something with the driven of magnetic field of star. When people explore the morphologies of most light curves from Kepler, they find that the light curves exhibit one or two dips during a single rotation [4]. Fitting the PSD well means capturing the frequency features of its counterparts in the space of time-flux/RV. Therefore, a general model as this one has the ability to capture single or double dip.

In Fig3, we use a sketch plot to illustrate the meaning of individual hyperparameters in SHO kernel (a) and display fitting results of solar irradiance (TSI) data of active phase (b) and quiet phase (c) individually, using the combination of SHO term (represents the rotation, in orange) and one SHO term (represents the super-granulation, in green), we do not add noise to our fitting results (total PSD are represented in red).

Figure 3: (a) Resonance curve described by SHO (credit Matthias, [Mechanical oscillations and resonances](#)), all of parameters in this illustration have the same physical meaning in our SHO kernel, but in different notation, α have the same meaning as $\frac{\omega_0^2}{4Q^2}$ in SHO. FWHM is derived as $\sqrt{3}\alpha$; (b) and (c) We use one year TSI data from the Solar Radiation and Climate Experiment (SORCE) as an example to explain the combination (in red) of two related SHO term (represents the rotation, in orange) plus one SHO term (represents the super-granulation, in green) fitting its power spectral density (PSD). Red curve is the model, black line is the PSD of one year TSI. We do not include noise in our model illustration here. (b) is at the active phase and (c) is at the quiet phase.

For the fitting procedure, we just fix the rotation period from photometry fitting and then leave the other hyperparameters for RV fitting free. During this part, we try to explore:

- **The recovery of stellar activity under different situations (simulations), e.g. fast and slow stellar rotator; active and inactive phase; long and short duration spots/plages, especially for Kepler solar-like stars**
- **Efficiency and false possibility towards solar-like stars activity RV variation mitigation**
- **Exploration of the relationship of hyper-parameters and spots/plages properties**
- **Distinguish the effect of granulation, especially supergranulation compared with spots/plages**
- **Applying our method to a RV-fitting test benchmark set in Dumusque [10]**

2.4. Benchmark Star for GP RV mitigation with photometry time series: HD 115043

There are two major GP-related methods in literature for how to reconstruct RV variability through stellar variability in photometry data. One is the FF' method proposed by Aigrain et al. [2]. Later works such as

Rajpaul et al. [41], they proposed that other activity indicators like $\log(R'_{HK})$, FWHM, BIS SPAN can make different contribution to the RV variation, might be the key to the fitting of RV time series from other flux indicators. Another method is pure GP, which does not consider physical bond between photometry and RV. A successful example for this method RV detection of Corot-7 system [19].

Within our test, we use two methods for analyzing HD 115043 which has 1373 good APT photometry measurements and 163 TOU RV observations. We find that both method can mitigate stellar activity in RV data withing the involvement of GP. But for $FF' + GP$ method, it seems GP takes all variations and the physical components coming from FF' which don't contribute much in the RV. Therefore, current $FF' + GP$ method has its own drawbacks, which we have discussed in part 1. These drawbacks may cause the invalidity of $FF' + GP$ when facing general situation. However, we can not discard this method because it has much greater potential to explore physical relationship between photometry and RV data. Since the final performances for these methods is similar and we haven't implemented test to quantify the limitation of $FF' + GP$ method, we just display the fitting result of pure GP in Fig.4

3. GP Hyper-parameter Exploration

3.1. GP robustness test of SOURCE TSI data

In order to constrain GP fitting of photometry and completely get variation from sunspots/plages and even granulations, we add one more SHO with fitting bound between the temporal resolution of time series and 3days into our GP model, which intends to capture the variation from supergranules. According to observations from Dopplergram measurement, it has a granulation component with timescale between 1 to 2 days. Unfortunately, the photometric intensity contrast at supergranulation scales in white light images is also much smaller and ambiguous than that of granulation, which has been shown to be up to 27% at a wavelength of 450 nm [46]. Several researchers claim that the temperature contrast in optical band is too small, around 0.8-2.8 K [32, 33, 16] and $\Delta T = 1.1 \pm 0.1K$ of the temperature drop between centre and edge of supergranules. [26]. However, some different voices reached out saying we still can detect their shadow in the psd of photometry:Aigrain et al. [1] to find supergranules with timescales around 1 day using VIRGO/SoHO lightcurves.

We use SOURCE TSI 6 hourly data with around 20-year observations to conduct our GP measurement. We successfully measure most rotation period at around 25 days and have two false detection in a quiet phase of the solar cycle. Our measurement of rotation period rate periodicity perfectly matches with solar cycle and butterfly diagram variation periodicity, but in some phase shifted with them(Fig5(a)). We also correlate hyperparameters variation with correct and false detection and discover that false detection appears when both Q factors in individual components of rotational term are smaller than $\frac{1}{2}$, which makes sense to us because we are dealing with non-resonance(oscillation) or critical/strong damping case physically. This range of Q_0 ($Q_0 < \frac{1}{2} - \frac{1}{2}$) locates in solar cycle quiet phase where granulations may dominate. However, we can not explain very well the physical of the oscillator with such regime with the granulation, which need further examinations.(Fig5(b))

3.2. Potential spots lifetime tracer from GP hyperparameters

Namekata et al. [38] developed a method to extract stellar spots lifetime and variation of spots area from Kepler lightcurves. This method is targeting stellar rotators with the temporal evolution of star spots showing clear emergence and decay without being disturbed by stellar differential rotation or granules. This inspires us to fit these portion of lightcurves using our GP model. We select 33 G-type Kepler star in their sample and run the same GP fitting towards yearly light curves. We visually check our fitting results and select those with false detection. We find that most false detections have clearly different mix values compared with those correct ones.(Fig6(a)) Therefore, we simply select those with mix smaller than 0.75 as reliable measurements. We expect to explore if we can find any relationship between some hyperparameters or their combination with spot lifetimes.

Except we find the same positive relationship between rotation periods and spots lifetime (Fig6(b)&Fig6(c)), which is not striking because we already constrain the rotation period measurement pretty well. Interestingly, we also find there is potential positive relationship between spots lifetime and the amplitude divided by full width at half maximum (FWHM) (Fig6(d)). This conclusion has great possibility to be confirmed if we get larger data sample and shrink the error-bar enough because this ratio $\frac{Amp}{FWHM}$ corresponds to the scenarios of which PSD have very weak oscillation bump. Physically, they are mostly weak damping situations, which means that the spots emerge very quickly and decay very quickly as well as compared to its rotation period. These spots always have a short lifetime.

Figure 4: Pure GP fitting HD115403 TOU RV data, addition term colored in purple comes from GP stochastic regression. Grey area is the overlapped range with APT photometrical observation

Figure 5: (a) Black dots are SOURCE TSI 6 hourly data within around 20 years. Orange dots are the emergence latitude distribution of solar spot at each Carrington Solar Coordinate obtained by the Royal Greenwich Observatory since 1874. Our GP measurement of solar sunspots rotation period variation can approximately match with solar cycle. The fitting also confirms that we can detect a quasi-period damping variation with timescales around 1 day from SOURCE TSI data. (b) Variation of hyperparameters during observations. Orange marks are the false measurements while green marks are correct ones. We notice that if both individual the Q factors of two SHO components is smaller than $\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}$, our GP can not completely capture the variation coming from sunspots rotation.

Figure 6: (a) We visually check our fitting results and label false detection (red dots) with correct ones (black dots). We find that mix value is good standard to rule out false measurements for this kind of stable rotation source without much differential and granules (b) shows a comparison between the rotational periods and lifetimes of star spots, and there looks to be a positive correlation in Namekata et al. [38]. There is an undetectable region because their algorithm can detect spots whose lifetimes are longer than a couple of rotational periods. (c) Same results using GP measurements. (d) We find that there is potential positive relationship between ratio $\frac{Amp}{FWMH}$ and spots lifetimes.

3.3. Rossby number and stellar activity

According to current knowledge of solar-like activity, the Rossby number is a quantity which can measure the effect of rotation imposed on convection. This dimensionless quantity first proposed in the field of planetary science, where people calculate it using the ratio of inertial force to Coriolis force. From its definition, a system with a small Rossby number have larger effect from Coriolis force than from the centrifugal force, which means that the system rotation effect is comparatively evident.

We select 164 G-type star from KOI catalog by filtering them with effective temperature from 5370K to 5980K and surface gravity from 4.32 to 4.48. We choose Kepler Pre-Search Data Conditioning lightcurves which have time resolution around 30 mins for each target. It is noticed that the scaling of scalable GP is with a scaling of $\mathcal{O}(N J^2)$, where J is the number of components in the mixture and N is the number of data points [15]. Therefore we bin the original Kepler lightcurve data with a window size equal to 13, which reconstructs the light curve with time resolution equal to around 0.27 days. We are confident that we can sample well defined quasi-period signals which have the timescale from 1 days to 3 days.

By doing this we hope to use our rotation GP kernel (mentioned in 2.1.1) plus another SHO component to capture super-granulation in the light curves. We have mentioned the the history of the shadow of super-granulation measurement from solar photometric variation in 3.3.1. While for stellar other than sun, very little work has been done to explore them. People have claimed to discover lower frequency signal in Corot light curve observations but explained them as microvariability caused by surface heterogeneities (for instance, the evolution of plage)instead of super-granulation.[22]

Since not all of stars have the same origin contributed to the stellar variability we observed in light curves, we need to classify our fitted light curves with both statistical rubric and visual check. First, we define those with mix value smaller than 0.75, one or two Q factors of both SHOs in rotation term larger than $\frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}$ and converged posterior distribution of rotation period as robust measurement of stellar spots rotation. Among 164 sources, we label 153 into this category. Then we continue subclassify them as rotation stable ones and rotation unstable ones. For rotation stable light curve, they might have relative rotation rate smaller than 0.3 for each yearly observation epoch if they have more than twice (not include twice) robust observation epochs, have rotation rate difference smaller than 5 days if they have twice robust observation epoch or if they just contain once robust observations and in reverse for unstable sources. Then we obtain 117 sources classified as stable rotation cases while the other 36 are threw into unstable category. Finally, we distinguish supergranulation(sG) detected sources (103) from sG non-detected ones (14) simply judging whether they have converged posterior distribution of characteristic frequency of the third SHO component.

For the estimation of Rossby number, since it is defined as the ratio of the rotation period to the convective turnover time at the bottom of the convective envelope ($\tau_{turnover}$). We determined the timescale of turnover from the equation 4 in Noyes et al. [39], which required us to know the $B - V$ color first. We take this color index directly from the UBV photometric survey in Kepler field by Everett et al. [13]. We successfully get the measurement of $\tau_{turnover}$ for 105 stable rotation sources and 11 for non-robust spots rotation ones (Fig 7(a)). We find there exits some bias in the convection turnover time between sG detected category and sG non-detected one and a slightly positive relationship between rotation period and convection turnover timescale (Fig7(b)). This confirms the same results in Landin et al. [25], where they claim that the existence of rotation tends to make $\tau_{turnover}$ higher than the non-rotating condition. This can be explained by the fact that one of the effect of rotation is to mimic a low mass star with thicker convective layers. They also find that differential stream in the stellar surface atmosphere will make $\tau_{turnover}$ smaller because the redistribution of fluid angular momentum and stellar winds leads to its lower angular velocity.

Many researchers have explored the relationship between single star parameter and stellar activity, especially rotation period.(e.g Noyes et al. [39], Basri et al. [3], Rutten [44], Jordan & Montesinos [23]). However, these relationships contain large scatter. While other author notice that rotation periods scaling with convective turnover time can effectively reduce such scattering and obtain a clear relationship.Montesinos et al. [35] compares different models and proves that the correlation of activity with Rossby number is significantly better than with rotation period alone. After getting a more accurate measurement of rotation period using GP towards our sources, we can observe a clearer correlation in Fig8(a) than in Fig8(b). Interestingly, we also find that sources without super-granulation detection tend to have larger rotation variations. This means that they contain larger spot areas or filling factor physically or they rotate faster (but since there is no very clear negative trend in period-amp relationship, the latter possibility is tiny compared with Rossby-amp relationship). In order to test if this conclusion is right, we need to increase the sample size in the left top corner (sources with larger variation from spots rotation but detect no super granulation)of Fig8(b). It is obvious that the detections are biased against those slow rotators but with small variation (right-bottom corner of Fig8(a)&Fig8(b)). Strkingly,

Figure 7: Fig7(a)(left)The histogram of $\tau_{turnover}$ calculated from Noyes et al. [39].The number of sources in non-rotating, rotating(super-granulation detected) and rotating(super-granulation non-detected) are 11, 91 and 14; Fig7(b)The convective turnover timescale against the rotation period showing a slightly positive trend of $\tau_{turnover}$ with P_{rot} .

when we plot the same relationship between Q-fatcot and Rossby-number, we find a clearer negative trend in it (Fig8(c)). The Q factor relates with the width of Lorentz profile directly. Since the wider the profile, the more significant the resonance peaks around the rotation period. We suppose that it has something with the rotation modulation and the emergence longitude of stellar spots but further conclusion need more tests from simulation.

4. Summary and Future Work

We develop a Julia code to simply simulate the temporal variation in flux and RV from star spots and plages considering the differential rotation, spots evolution and long term magnetic cycle. In our code, we find that the existence of plages will make the time series tend to be less periodic or false prediction of true periods (always predict their nth harmonics). For simulations with period from 3 to 80 days, our GP can accurately find their rotation period. And GP is proved to be available towards our TOU RV benchmark, the star HD115403.

When we exclude those false detections given by GP, we also run our GP fitting to SOURCE TSI observation and successfully measure the rotation periods and granulation timescales. Yearly solar sunspot rotation period variation rate and timescale of super-granulation rate can approximately match with solar cycle.

We then apply our pipeline into the G-type stars in Namekata et al. [38] measured sources and we also find a positive correlation between spots lifetime and rotation period. The ratio of amplitude and FWHM from GP rotation kernel seems to be a good tracer for spots lifetime (positive trend between these two values), but the scattering error of this relationship is large. We need more samples to confirm whether it is real or not.

Finally, in GP fitting we explore the hyper-parameters distribution for different morphologies of light curves from KOI catalog. We conduct our measurement of 164 KOI G-type stars. For those light curves with signal that is not detected to have super-granulation, they tend to have larger variability. The Rossby number is a better tracer for the variability caused by spots rotation than rotation period itself. Currently our results are constrained within KOI G-type stars, but if we expand the sample size and extend into other type stars a more apparent relationship like this should be observed. We find Q factor have much more robust negative trend with increasing Rossby number, but the physics of such relationship remains unknown. We need use our simulation code to produce samples with different Q to confirm this relationship, which also depends the future implementation of the simulation of convection flows.

Though our simulation is extremely simple and does not consider the effect of activity to the stellar spectrum, we step as the first to understand the physical bond in the stellar activity between photometric proxies and RV. More real and physical-motivated simulation including convection compression, different surface fluid phenomena such as meridional flow will help us map the flux to RV map better.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 8: Comparing (a) with (b), we find that Rossby number is better tracer for the variability caused by spots rotation. In addition, sources with no supergranulation detected seem to have larger variability and shorter convective turnover time; (c) We find that the Q factor has a much more robust negative trend with increasing Rossby number, but the physics of such relationship remains unknown.

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